

ASSESSMENT OF THE TECHNOLOGICAL PROFICIENCY OF TEACHING AND NON-TEACHING STAFF OF SAN CARLOS COLLEGE

Jennia A. Olalia^{1,3}, Maynard Gel F. Carse^{2,3}, Aldrich Michael B. Garcia³
ICT Extension Staff¹, Technical Specialist², Faculty³

Abstract. This study assesses the knowledge and skills of the teaching and non-teaching staff of San Carlos College to identify training requirements for the improvement of their work quality and production. It deals with basic technology skills used in everyday work whether it be in teaching or admin work. This includes word processing, slide presentations, spreadsheets, searching the internet, email and communication, and general knowledge.

Keywords. Needs Assessment, Technological Proficiency, Training Development Plan

1 Introduction

In the rapidly evolving digital age, technology proficiency has become an essential skill set for every individual, especially in the educational sector. The need for technology proficiency training for school employees is paramount, as it directly impacts the quality of education and the overall learning environment.

A Training Needs Assessment (TNA) is a systematic process of identifying and analyzing the areas where school employees need to improve their technology skills. This assessment helps in determining the gaps between the current skills of the employees and the required skills to effectively utilize the technology tools available in the school.

The introduction of technology proficiency training based on a TNA ensures that the training is tailored to meet the specific needs of the employees, thereby enhancing their ability to integrate technology into their daily tasks. This not only improves the efficiency and effectiveness of the school operations but also prepares the school community to adapt to the ever-changing technological landscape.

A study conducted by De La Salle University – Manila discusses the translation of technology to society and how it has been an object of interest since the 1980s (Nueva, 2019). The study reveals that technology is used in the classroom for instructional support, information referencing, and as a communication and collaboration platform. Teachers experienced digital inequality due to their digital competency gap, belief, and institutional perception of the function of technology in the classroom.

A study (Fu, 2013) summarizes the relevant research on the use of information and communication technology (ICT) in education. It discusses the merits of ICT integration in schools, barriers or challenges encountered in the use of ICT, factors influencing successful ICT integration, and in-service and pre-service teachers' attitudes, perceptions, and confidence in using ICT.

The demand for Technology Integration as schools were required to keep up with the 21st-century learners (Rosalies, 2021). It emphasizes the importance of understanding how to adapt technology in the pedagogy of each subject area, how to equip teachers through continuous training programs, and most importantly, moving towards professional development to empower the teachers.

Another study assesses the impact of emerging technology integration on the knowledge and skills acquisition of K-12 students in the Philippines (Dublar, 2023). The study identifies the challenges and opportunities in the integration of these technologies in education.

Conducting technology proficiency training based on a TNA is a strategic approach to empower school employees with the necessary skills, fostering a technologically advanced educational environment that benefits both the staff and the students. It is an investment in the future, paving the way for a technologically proficient and innovative educational institution.

2 Research Methodology

This study made use of the descriptive-developmental method of research. It looked into personal evaluation or assessment of San Carlos College's employees in the area of technological proficiency. A Technological Proficiency Survey was administered to both teaching and non-teaching staff. There are a total of 35 respondents from different departments such as the basic education, tertiary, and graduate school departments, administration office, registrar, and even the general services. Convenience Sampling was used for the identification of the population of the survey.

The survey involves questions that assess the employees' expertise in basic technological areas used in their every work. This includes Email and Communication, Word Processing, Spreadsheets, Slide Presentations, Searching the Internet, and General Knowledge.

The survey instrument was printed and administered to the respondents. Alongside, an online form of the same survey instrument was created and used to analyze and graph the results by encoding respondent's answers in the online form. Some options in the survey are intended to include wrong answers to determine the knowledge of the respondents, especially on research content and sources.

Rating on each item uses the Lickert scale to determine their capacity to perform it. The scale is described below:

- | | |
|---|---------------------------------|
| 1 | Have No Idea |
| 2 | Have an Idea but no Experience |
| 3 | Can Barely Do |
| 4 | Can Do With Minimal Supervision |
| 5 | Expert |

No statistical treatment was used because the answers were interpreted directly from how it was graphed.

3 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

3.1 Email and Communication

Figure 1. Proficiency in Sending and Receiving Emails

When asked if “I can read emails and respond to emails properly”, most of the respondents agreed that they are “Experts” on doing it followed by 9 respondents who say they can do it with minimal supervision. Additionally, the majority of the respondents said that they know how to attach files in an email. However, sending emails with multiple recipients and using carbon copy and blind carbon copy is a concern and needs to be addressed.

Communication using known apps might not be a problem with the employees of San Carlos College. Asked if they know how to use social media messaging apps like Messenger and Viber, the overwhelming majority can at least do it with minimal supervision. The same result can be seen in Figure 2 about sending text and making calls. Additionally, most of the employees know how to post, react, and comment on articles posted on social media platforms. Video conferencing is also a simple task for the employees whether they are using Zoom or Google Meet for online meetings.

Figure 2. Proficiency in Using Apps in Communication

3.2 Word-Processing

Word processing should be a given skill or knowledge not only for teachers but also for non-teaching staff. The following are the results of the survey:

Figure 3. Familiarity with Basic Word Processing Functions

According to the respondents, the vast majority know how to create and format text in a word-processing application. They know how to insert or integrate images, shapes, and tables with text. This includes laying them together with other objects within the document. Although some are not aware of other word-processing applications aside from Microsoft Word, most of them use other applications. Although uncommon in the workplace, the majority of the respondents know how to do a mail merge to create documents with changing fields but the same content such as letters and other correspondence.

Figure 4. Familiarity with Basic Word Processing Functions

To communicate the content of the document, employees should know how to generate portable formats such as PDFs and print them as per requirement. As expected, the majority of the respondents know how to export documents in PDF format and print them according to specifications such as margins, collations, scaling, and orientation. They also know other word-processing applications aside from Microsoft Word.

3.3 Spreadsheet

Spreadsheet knowledge and skills are a must not only for teachers (in computing grades) but also for non-teaching employees alike. This application can help solve basic accounting problems and computations. When asked if the respondents understand how the cells work, a fraction say they barely know it. This is alarming since the next question's result doesn't fit right with the latter result. When asked if they know how to use basic mathematical formulas in cells, most of them answer they "can do it with minimal supervision".

Figure 5. Familiarity with Spreadsheet Applications

Referencing can be difficult if not properly utilized. Problems such as circular referencing can happen. Thus, correct referencing is a must. When asked if the respondents understood the difference between the two methods, the majority knew with minimal supervision. They also know how to integrate basic mathematical functions for basic computation.

Graphing describes data knowledgeably and interestingly. The selection of appropriate graphs based on actual data is a necessary skill. The interesting answer comes out when the respondents know how to select and use appropriate graphs based on data, scales 3, 4, and 5 are statistically even. This means that although a third of the respondents are experts on graphs and another third can do graphs with minimal supervision, another third says they can barely do it. Surprisingly, there are a lot of respondents who can barely do pivot tables or don't even have an idea about pivot tables.

Figure 6. Familiarity with Function, Graph, and Pivot Tables

Figure 7. Familiarity with Function, Graph, and Pivot Tables

Compared to exporting in word-processing applications, some respondents are having a hard time exporting a sheet into a CSV or PDF format. However, printing a spreadsheet file poses no problem for respondents except for several respondents who can barely do it. When asked if they know other spreadsheet applications, respondents said they know other applications although 5 of the respondents don't have idea other spreadsheet application exists.

3.4 Slide Presentation

Presentation skills using slides can make communication easier. With some available slide presentation applications on the market today, an employee needs to have a basic knowledge of it. Respondents are very positive they know how to insert, remove, duplicate, and edit slides within the presentation with 21 votes. The same votes were gathered about the respondents' knowledge of how to import and use templates. On applying animations and transitions, most of the respondents can do it. Most employees also know how to integrate images, shapes, and tables with text in the slide.

Figure 8. Familiarity with Slide Presentation Application

Figure 9. Familiarity with Links, Slide Master, and Printing

Figure 10. Familiarity with Videos, Exports, and Other Slide Presentations

Inserting links, files or URLs can be easily done by the respondents as depicted in Figure 9. They also know how to print handouts with a different number of slides per paper. However, a rise in the 3 - Can Barely Do level can be seen when asked about using and editing slide masters. It is understandable since slide masters are discussed but very important. The same goes with the item Recording Videos Using the Same Slide and exporting the slide into video, still images, and PDF files. Still, the respondents are familiar with other slide presentation applications aside from Microsoft PowerPoint.

3.5 Searching the Internet

Figure 11. Searching and Copying from the Internet

The internet is the richest source of information in the information age. Having the knowledge and skills in searching the internet is a must in today's workforce. An overwhelming majority of the respondents know how to search the internet for facts from authoritative sources and thus have an idea of how to spot true and fake content. They also know how to

copy assets such as images and integrate them into applications such as word processors, spreadsheets, slide presentations, and emails.

Figure 12. Downloading and Image Processing

Generally, respondents know how to download files from different sources such as websites and torrents. They also know how to download videos and/or convert them to audio files using web applications. Most of them also know how to do basic image processing such as removal of image background for integration to desktop applications.

3.6 General Knowledge

As for the general knowledge questions, the users are all familiar with and using mobile devices and personal computers, whether they own them or borrow them. They claim that they type well using proper typing positions. Most of them also claim that they know how to install new applications on their computer and mobile phones. They are also aware of the unwanted programs that might creep inside their computer systems.

Figure 13. Computer Operation and Security

Additionally, Figure 14 shows that respondents claim they are using strong passwords. It can also be ruled out that they know the right combination of strong passwords. Most of them have no problem installing new equipment to the computer such as printers and scanners. It also follows that proper drivers were downloaded and installed. Since the employees mostly agree that they know how the export files from a word processor, spreadsheet, and slide presentation, most of them answered affirmative in knowing what a PDF file is.

Figure 14. Common Knowledge and Safety Issues

Computer operation can be productive at the same time might pose a risk to the health and safety of the employee. When asked if they are aware of basic health and safety issues, the overwhelming majority answer affirmatively. On the other note, connecting smart devices to Bluetooth and WiFi poses no problem with the work of the employees including how to properly take care of their equipment and devices. However, there is a slight lack of confidence in the part of basic troubleshooting and repair of computer equipment and the extension of display in a second screen such as monitor and projectors.

Figure 15. Basic Repair, Connectivity, and Care

4 Conclusion and Recommendation

Most of the respondents know how to communicate online using emails, instant messenger, and video conferencing apps which is a good indication that employees have a good grasp on modern communication tools despite their age difference. An exemption on the knowledge of sending multiple emails with carbon and blind carbon copy which the employee admitted not to be very familiar with.

On word-processing, most teaching and non-teaching staff are capable of using word-processing software in creating letters, reports, and others. They know how to integrate text with tables, images, shapes, and others. They are also knowledgeable in exporting the document into PDF and printing it accordingly.

Working on spreadsheets, a slight decline in answers can be seen. Although overall the result is still on a positive note, the knowledge level shifted from 5 - Expert to 4 - Can Do With Minimal Supervision. This can be because spreadsheets are less used compared to word-processing software.

A comeback on the result can also be noted with the answers of the respondents about their knowledge and skills in creating slide presentations. Like with the word-processing, the overwhelming answers are on the Expert level. However, there can be a consistent answer of 1 - Have No Idea with 1-2 votes from word processing, spreadsheet, and slide

presentation. This consistency can be attributed to at least 2 employees who have no foundation in computer and software operations which needs to be addressed.

To meet the needs of the respondents and equip them with proper knowledge and skills in research, a 2-day face-to-face workshop seminar (preferably with mentoring) with a guest expert is recommended.

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